

FLAME RETARDANT KENAF/PLA BIOCOMPOSITES: EFFECT OF AMMONIUM POLYPHOSPHATE

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Keywords: *flame retardancy, biocomposites, kenaf, PLA, ammonium polyphosphate*

1 Introduction

Flame retardancy of plastics and composites is critically important in related industries. Polymers, which are hydrocarbon-based organic materials, are subject to flame and toxic gases upon firing and, in general, have poor flame resistance. Accordingly, flame-resistant polymers are needed in the applications subject to flame. In particular, flame-retardancy is critically important in fiber-reinforced plastics for safety regulation requirement [1-3].

Industries and academia, which have been dealing with fiber-reinforced polymer composites, have been seeking for environmentally-benign composite materials with flame retardancy [3,4]. Natural fiber-reinforced biocomposites are less expensive, biodegradable, and also contributing to the reduction of carbon dioxide during the cultivation [5]. In addition, they are light-weight due to low density of natural fibers, good mechanical properties and abrasion resistance [4]. For many years, therefore, natural fiber-reinforced biocomposites have been utilized to replace glass fiber-reinforced composites due to their advantages with natural fibers [6-8].

Recently, poly(lactic acid) (PLA) has also been increasingly studied as alternative of a synthetic polypropylene. PLA is the most promising biodegradable polymer resin with good mechanical properties and processibility [9-11]. However, uses of PLA are restricted due to its low flame resistance [12-14]. Therefore, it would be desirable if PLA exhibits improved flame retardancy. In particular, once PLA is utilized in automobile and building interiors, electronic parts and housings [15]. Kenaf is one of the most utilized cellulose-based natural fibers in biocomposite systems.

A number of papers on kenaf/PLA biocomposites

have been reported during the past years [12,16-18]. However, studies on the flame retardancy on kenaf/PLA biocomposites have been rarely found. Consequently, the objective of the work is to investigate how incorporation of ammonium polyphosphate (APP) into PLA matrix influences the flame retardancy, thermal stability, thermo-dimensional stability, and the dynamic mechanical and tensile properties of kenaf/PLA biocomposites, in terms of limiting oxygen index (LOI), thermal decomposition, thermal expansion, tensile modulus and strength, storage modulus, and $\tan \delta$.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Kenaf fibers used in this work were supplied from Bangladesh. Ammonium polyphosphate (APP) used as flame retardant was purchased from Chemizone Inc., Korea. PLA (Grade 2003D) was purchased from NatureWorks®.

2.2 Processing of Kenaf/PLA Biocomposites

A twin screw extruder (BT-30-S2-421, LG Machine Co., Korea) was used to compound PLA and APP. The screw diameter was 30 mm each and the L/D ratio of 42. The screw speed was 130 rpm and the feeding rate was 5.5 kg/h. The barrel temperature was in the range of 130~180°C. Kenaf/PLA biocomposites were made by compression molding using PLA pellets containing APP and chopped kenaf fibers. The fiber contents were 40 wt%. The APP contents varied from 0 to 50 wt%. The 'as-supplied' kenaf fibers were chopped to about 3 mm in average. The dimensions of the biocomposites obtained were 150 mm x 100 mm x 3.5 mm.

2.3 Characterization

The LOI test was conducted at ambient temperature using a vertical-type oxygen index tester (FTT Co.) according to ISO 4589 [19]. The specimen dimensions were 80 mm long, 10 mm wide and 3.5 mm thick. UL-94 test was also performed according to ASTM D 3801 [20] using UL-94 vertical flame chamber (Fire Testing Technology: FTT Co.) in order to evaluate the flame resistance of kenaf/PLA biocomposites loaded with APP. The dimensions of each specimen were 127 mm x 12.7 mm x 3.5 mm.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA Q500, TA Instruments) was carried out using a can-type alumina pan to 500°C purging a nitrogen gas to examine the thermal stability of PLA and kenaf/PLA biocomposites. The heating rate was 20°C/min. Thermomechanical analysis (TMA 2940, TA instruments) was performed using an expansion mode to 150°C purging a nitrogen gas to explore the thermal expansion behavior. The heating rate was 5°C/min. DMA (Q800, TA Instruments) was used to measure the storage modulus, loss modulus and $\tan \delta$ of each composite. A dual cantilever mode was applied. Each DMA measurement was performed from 30 to 150°C with the heating rate of 3°C/min and the oscillation amplitude of 0.2 mm at 1 Hz. The specimen dimensions were 60 mm long, 12 mm wide and 3.5 mm thick.

Tensile tests were conducted using a universal testing machine (UTM, AG-50kNX, Shimadzu) according to DIN 53 445. The crosshead speed was 5 mm/min. The load cell of 50 kN was used. The specimen dimensions were 150 mm x 15 mm x 3.5 mm. Average tensile strength and modulus were obtained from 10 specimens of each composite. A scanning electron microscope (JSM 6380, JEOL) was used to observe the surfaces of PLA and the biocomposites fractured by tensile testing. The electron beam voltage was fixed to 10 keV. The SEM images were obtained using a secondary electron image (SEI) method. All the specimens were platinum-coated by sputtering.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Flame Retardancy

Fig. 1 displays photos taken by a digital camera for the specimens remained after the LOI test with various kenaf/PLA biocomposites. The following describes the LOI testing procedure. Given for the kenaf/PLA biocomposite specimens shown in Fig.

1A, the first specimen was ignited in the presence of a certain oxygen concentration in air and checked out the specimen loss of 5 cm for 3 min. Once the specimen was not consumed for the duration of 3 min, the first test was temporarily stopped and then the oxygen concentration was increased slightly for the second specimen. This procedure was repeated with the increment of oxygen concentration by 0.2% until the 5 cm in length was consumed or lost from the top of each specimen for 3 min.

Fig. 1. Photos for the specimens before (left) and after (right) LOI test with kenaf/PLA biocomposites without (A) and with various APP loadings (B to E). B: 10 wt%, C: 20 wt%, D: 30 wt%, E: 50 wt%.

The five specimens in each figure from A to E represent a series of biocomposites from the beginning to the end of LOI test, displaying their appearances at each testing stage. The far left specimen represents the beginning stage of the test and the far right one shows the ending stage of the test. The tested specimens in the corresponding testing stage looked similar, as seen in each figure from A to E. However, the amount of oxygen required for the LOI test was varied depending on flame retarding capability of the biocomposite specimen, resulting in different LOI values, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 compares the limiting oxygen index values among kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with APP at various loadings. The LOI values 23.9, 32.1, 35.2, 38.4, and 45.3, which were obtained from the fifth specimens of each sample, are shown in Fig. 1. The higher LOI value the greater flame retardancy of the biocomposite sample. The LOI value of the composite without APP was 23.9. The value was gradually increased with increasing the APP content from 32.1 for 10 wt% to 45.3 for 50 wt% APP, exhibiting an improvement of the flame retardancy of about 90%. This remarkable increase in the LOI value indicated that APP played an effective role in retarding the flammability of kenaf/PLA biocomposites.

Table 1 also indicates whether the present kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with APP were failed or passed by the UL-94 test. V-0 indicates the specimens were passed according to the standard ISO 4589. The result reflected that the LOI value should be higher than 35 to be successful for the UL-94 test and the higher value would be good to be a flame retardant biocomposite material. The correlation between the LOI and UL-94 results has been found in other studies [14,21-23].

Table 1. LOI values and UL-94 test result of kenaf/PLA biocomposites with various APP loadings

APP in PLA (wt%)	0	10	20	30	50
LOI Test	23.9	32.1	35.2	38.4	45.3
UL-94 Test	Fail	Fail	V-0	V-0	V-0

It was concluded based on the LOI and UL-94 test results that APP acted as an excellent flame retardant of kenaf/PLA biocomposite, resulting in the

increased LOI value, as similarly found in other literatures [24,25].

3.2 Thermal Stability

Fig. 2 shows the variations of the thermal stability of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with APP. The kenaf/PLA biocomposites without APP exhibited obvious weight loss above about 270°C and abrupt weight loss above 300°C down to 370°C. Its thermal stability was greatest up to about 330°C among the samples measured. It was clear that with the addition of APP to the kenaf/PLA the thermal stability above 330°C was apparently increased with increasing the APP loading [3,26]. The residual weights near 500°C were about 1, 13, 25, 30 and 40% for 0, 10, 20, 30 and 50 wt% APP, respectively [26,27].

Fig. 2. TG (top) and DTG (bottom) curves measured in N₂ for kenaf/PLA biocomposites without (A) and with various APP loadings (B to E).

According to the derivative thermogravimetric (DTG) curves, the incorporation of APP shifted the fastest

weight loss temperature to the higher temperature region by about 20°C. The small peaks in the range of 270 to 320°C were due to the presence of APP in the PLA matrix, leading to an additional weight loss around 300°C, as seen in the thermogravimetric (TG) curves.

3.3 Thermo-dimensional Stability

Fig. 3 represents the thermal expansion behavior of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with APP, showing the thermo-dimensional change as a function of temperature. Overall, the thermo-dimensional stability was higher in the kenaf/PLA biocomposites with APP than that without APP even though the specimen without APP exhibited a slightly higher stability in the low temperature region of 50-80°C.

Fig. 3. TMA curves measured with kenaf/PLA biocomposites without (A) and with various APP loadings (B to E) as a function of temperature.

Table 2. CTE values measured at different temperature regions for kenaf/PLA biocomposites with various APP loadings

Biocomposite	CTE ($\mu\text{m}/^\circ\text{C}$)		
	50~80°C	80~120°C	120~150°C
0APP-PLA	0.393	1.010	1.672
10APP-PLA	0.652	0.868	1.193
20APP-PLA	0.500	0.634	0.901
30APP-PLA	0.392	0.528	0.780
50APP-PLA	0.278	0.369	0.544

The coefficients of thermal expansion, which were determined from the slope of each TMA curve, were lower in the biocomposites with APP than without APP, as summarized in Table 2. Also, the CTE values decreased with increasing the APP loading. The CTE of kenaf/PLA biocomposites with 50 wt% APP was 61-67% lower than that without APP, particularly at above 80°C.

3.4 Dynamic Mechanical Properties

Fig. 4 displays the dynamic mechanical properties of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with APP at various loadings. The storage modulus was considerably increased with increasing APP loading [28]. Only with the addition of 10 wt% APP, the storage modulus of kenaf/PLA biocomposite was remarkably increased in comparison to the sample without APP. At room temperature, the storage modulus of the composite with 50 wt% APP was about 3 times greater than that without APP and about 40% higher than that with 10 wt% APP. At 80°C, it was found that the modulus enhancement was much larger.

Fig. 4. Storage modulus and $\tan \delta$ of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without (A) and with different APP loadings (B to E).

The biocomposite without APP exhibited about 300 MPa at 80°C whereas the biocomposite with 50 wt% APP exhibited about 4100 MPa. It reflects that the incorporation of a flame retardant APP into the PLA matrix made the biocomposite stiffer. In addition, the kenaf/PLA biocomposites with 30 wt% APP and higher did not show the upward curve in the range of 90-110°C, which was resulted from recrystallization of PLA matrix resin during the measurement. $\tan \delta$ peak temperature, which can be referred to as glass transition temperature, was shifted to a higher temperature with increasing the APP content. The peak height, which can be related with the damping property of a material, was markedly decreased with the ATH content, reflecting a reinforcing effect by APP as well as by kenaf fibers.

3.5 Tensile Properties

Fig. 5 shows the tensile modulus, tensile strength and elongation at break of kenaf/PLA biocomposites as a function of APP content incorporated in the PLA matrix. The tensile modulus was gradually increased with increasing the APP loading [21], indicating about a 35% improvement from 3.4 GPa at 0 wt% APP to 4.6 GPa at 50 wt% APP. This improvement was agreed with the improvement of the storage modulus in the DMA result, leading to a stiffening of the kenaf/PLA biocomposite. It has been studied earlier [29,30] that kenaf fibers effectively contributed to enhancing both dynamic storage modulus and tensile modulus. The modulus was increased with increasing the kenaf up to an optimal loading. It is said that the incorporation of APP in the PLA matrix to make kenaf/PLA biocomposite can play a role not only in providing flame retardancy to the biocomposite but also in further enhancing the modulus. It was expected that the addition of APP higher than 50 wt% might be detrimental to the mechanical properties because there were some dispersion difficulties in processing APP/PLA pellets by means of twin-screw extrusion technique. This is why we did not extend our study with kenaf/PLA biocomposites including APP higher than 50 wt%. The tensile strength of the biocomposite was gradually decreased with increasing the APP loading [31]. It indicates that APP may cause microstructural defects in the PLA matrix and the micro-defects may be locally existed more. Percent elongation at break of the biocomposite was slight increased with increasing the APP, showing about 2% increase at 50 wt% APP. Therefore it may be said that APP was

Fig. 5. Comparisons of tensile modulus (A), strength (B), and elongation at break (C) of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with various APP loadings.

weak and soft, compared to PLA. It is, in other words, stressed that APP played a triple role in the kenaf/PLA biocomposite: effective flame retardant, stiffening and toughening filler.

3.6 Fracture Surface Observations

Fig. 6 shows the scanning electron microscopic images of the fractured surfaces of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without and with various APP loadings. It was observed that the matrix part of the fractured surfaces became rough with increasing the APP. It seems that the PLA matrix is brittle, as expected. This slightly changing surface roughness of the matrix was consistent with the variation of the elongation at break of the PLA-based biocomposite. It was also found that the interfacial bonding between the kenaf fiber and the PLA matrix was poor in the biocomposite without APP and with 10 wt% APP. However, the interfacial bonding was relatively good in the higher APP loadings. It is likely that this SEM result more or less support the thermal and mechanical result qualitatively.

4 Conclusions

- 1) PLA pellets including ammonium polyphosphate (APP) at various contents were successfully processed by means of twin-screw extrusion technique.
- 2) Kenaf/PLA biocomposites incorporated with APP had good flame retardancy, particularly indicating the LOI value of 45.3 and the V-0 level of UL-94 test at 50 wt% APP.
- 3) The thermal stability at high temperature region above 350°C and the thermo-dimensional stability studied in terms of coefficient of thermal expansion were increased with increasing APP contents.
- 4) The dynamic storage and tensile moduli were considerably increased with increasing APP contents.
- 5) The incorporation of APP into PLA matrix decreased the tensile strength but increased the elongation at break.

In conclusions, flame-retardant kenaf/PLA biocomposites were successfully developed by introducing APP into PLA at an appropriate loading. It was noticed that APP simultaneously played a triple role in the kenaf/PLA biocomposite: an effective flame retardant, a stiffening filler, and a toughening filler.

Fig. 6. SEM images of the fractured surfaces of kenaf/PLA biocomposites without (A) and with various APP loadings. B: 10 wt%, C: 20 wt%, D: 30 wt%, E: 50 wt%.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Research Fund, Kumoh National Institute of Technology, Gumi, Korea.

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